

Knowledge-driven federated learning

1 - Features in the final version

The final step of our work involves applying our approach to a pilot use case. The goal is to determine how, from a single series of data obtained from one meter (main consumption), we can identify the consumption of individual appliances based on aggregate measurements.

The developed features are:

- Introduction and development of Temporal Convolutional networks (TCN) on top of the LSTM
- Development of the API
- Connection to the Data Space (through TSG Connector)

These features aim for the:

- Prediction of the types of appliances (dishwasher, fridge + freezer, washing machine, dryer, oven)
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- Prediction of on/off time consumption of each appliance over time (very good accuracy)
- Prediction of energy consumption (low accuracy) The feature does not predict the consumption of unknown appliances, but the model can be retrained if additional appliances are included in the ground truth data.

In this context, we utilised the power disaggregation method, which separates the consumption values of individual appliances from the total power usage. In machine learning, this process is known as Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM). However, all NILM models in the literature are non-causal (LSTM, RNN, etc.) and require future values for disaggregation at the current time step t . This is why we introduced this new feature (Temporal Convolutional Networks).

2-Front-end

Below it is presented the service front-end. For each household (Home) we can have the consumption graph of each appliance in time (we have five appliances to track at the moment) derived from the main. The front end receives data from the backend in a CSV file. By clicking on a household, you can load the main file containing input. Then, the front end will call the backend to get the data needed for each appliance.

Input :

The csv file that contains date and main energy consumption should cotains these fields (datetime and energy)

```
datetime,energy
2022-08-31 23:00:00,0.167
2022-08-31 23:15:00,0.164
2022-08-31 23:30:00,0.155
2022-08-31 23:45:00,0.165
2022-09-01 00:00:00,0.158
2022-09-01 00:15:00,0.149
2022-09-01 00:30:00,0.157
2022-09-01 00:45:00,0.154
2022-09-01 01:00:00,0.138
2022-09-01 01:15:00,0.147
2022-09-01 01:30:00,0.149
2022-09-01 01:45:00,0.143
2022-09-01 02:00:00,0.141
2022-09-01 02:15:00,0.151
2022-09-01 02:30:00,0.155
2022-09-01 02:45:00,0.142
2022-09-01 03:00:00,0.145
2022-09-01 03:15:00,0.143
2022-09-01 03:30:00,0.136
2022-09-01 03:45:00,0.128
2022-09-01 04:00:00,0.132
2022-09-01 04:15:00,0.128
2022-09-01 04:30:00,0.132
2022-09-01 04:45:00,0.144
2022-09-01 05:00:00,0.137
2022-09-01 05:15:00,0.118
2022-09-01 05:30:00,0.112
2022-09-01 05:45:00,0.111
2022-09-01 06:00:00,0.131
```

The interface for uploading the input :

Enershare FL NILM

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Then by click on submit, you have the consumption of each appliance in time. You can choose the appliance of your choice to visualize.

Enershare FL NILM

mains.csv

Service documentation

While the software is not open source, the structure of the implementation, outlining the available endpoints, their functionalities, and requirements, can be found in <https://bensley7.github.io/3D-reconstruction/>

Indeed, in POST mode, we use the ENGIE URL of the API (predict function) as the only endpoint using the user credentials. The output is a CSV file, that has appliances predicted as columns, with the energy consumption of each appliance by timestamp. In this context, we can find the link for the REST API [here](#)

Licensing

The code is proprietary to ENGIE and is maintained in a closed-source format. A video that demonstrates the service can be found on the project website.

Integration and deployment with Data Space

The service is integrated with the TSG Connector from TNO and in the AppStore from the ENERSHARE marketplace.